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International experience in implementing a dual form of education into the system before higher and higher professional education of Ukraine

***Abstract.** The article considers duality as a methodological characteristic of vocational education; the essence of the dual form of education is revealed; the legal basis for the introduction of the dual form of education in vocational institutions before higher and higher education of Ukraine has been determined; the results of the research conducted in institutions before higher and higher professional education of four regions of Ukraine "Expert assessment of students of future professional activity" are given; the peculiarities of the dual system of education of the EU countries are characterized; The peculiarities of the practice of using dual form of education, public-private partnership on the implementation of the Concept of Development of the National Technical University "Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute" for 2016-2025 with IT companies, in particular the Project of dual approach to education in training IT masters at the Department of Software Engineering and information technology management "NTU" KhPI "; the experience of active interaction of the Career Center of the National Technical University "Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute" with the employers of the companies "AltBier", "Procter & Gambel", Landstar Agent Ukraine is presented; noted that the further development of social partnership, consolidation of efforts of central and local executive bodies and local governments, educational institutions, employers, scientists and the public will contribute to raising higher and higher professional education to a qualitatively new level; it is proved that the introduction of dual education will allow employers to participate in the process of training graduates, and the use of experience of dual education in the EU before higher and higher vocational*

education will contribute to better training of students and their demand in the Ukrainian and world labor markets; The influence of the process of digitalization on the professional training of students is outlined in the perspective direction of further research.

Keywords: *dual form of education, strategy, pre-higher and higher education, international experience, legal framework, professional activity, employers, labor market.*

Problem statement in general and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. The mission of higher education in Ukraine is to ensure sustainable innovative development of the state through the training of highly qualified specialists, the creation and dissemination of knowledge, the formation of intellectual, social and spiritual capital of a society ready for the challenges of the future. One of the tasks of the operational goal of the Strategy for the Development of Higher Education in Ukraine for 2021-2031 is to create a mechanism for cooperation between the higher education system and the labor market; raising the level of practical training of students; development of distance, full-time and part-time, dual and mixed forms of education; approval of the Regulations on the dual form of higher and professional pre-higher education and the Standard Agreement on the acquisition of higher and professional pre-higher education in dual form, development of the "Strategy for the development of dual education"; development and introduction of a mechanism to take into account the interests of employers, the needs of regional labor markets in the formation of state and regional orders for training; introduction of a mechanism to stimulate enterprises, institutions, organizations of all forms of ownership to provide the first job to graduates of higher education institutions [7].

Analysis of recent research and publications. The issue of training specialists in the dual form of education is the subject of research by foreign researchers, including M. Tribus, whose study revealed the use of the principles of total quality management (TQM) in education, provided suggestions for working with four systems to be considered in implementation quality management in any enterprise: education system, management system, social system, as well as tools and methods [9]; F. Lunenburg and A. Ornstein [11], who proposed the best management methods in

business, management theory, research and practice, the most effective in modern educational contexts; F. Yasharevich, E. Cook [10], in whose works the main determinants, place and role of non-formal education and lifelong learning in the context of development of both individuals and wider social groups are analyzed; proved the crucial importance of management and its impact on the creation of a system of non-formal education in Bosnia and Herzegovina, which will provide sustainable training for employees to meet modern labor market requirements as one of the main competitive advantages of countries with such a system.

The European experience of dual learning is analyzed in the works of domestic scientists V. Vemyan [2], L. Gren [3; 34], S. Drazhnytsia [4], B. Mokina [7], S. Karliuk [3], O. Kosaruk [7], V. Ter-Hovhannisyan [2]. Thus, in the works of V. Vemyan and V. Ter-Hovhannisyan the essence and significance of the dual system of vocational education and educational activities on the use of foreign experience in organizing the educational process are analyzed, the modular system of vocational training is considered as an innovative concept that radically changes the approach to its organization) [2]; S. Drazhnyts' research revealed problems that prevent the introduction of dual education in domestic vocational education, proposed a structural model of vocational training on a dual basis [5]; directions of using the dual form of education in the system of higher education in Germany and the possibility of their implementation in higher technical institutions of Ukraine were considered in the studies of L. Gren, S. Karliuk, Y. Panfilov [3]; The ideology of improving the quality of engineering education through the parallel development of students of working professions that correlate with engineering, is set out in scientific articles B. Mokina, O. Kosaruk [7].

The purpose of the article. To reveal the elements of introduction of the experience of the dual form of education of the EU countries into the system of higher professional education of Ukraine.

Presenting main material. The need to introduce dual education in the system of training specialists in higher education institutions of Ukraine is caused by the

problem of lack of practical skills of graduates and their unpreparedness for professional activity (61% of respondents from among employers confirmed this fact).

Duality as a methodological characteristic of vocational education presupposes coordinated interaction of the educational and industrial spheres for the training of specialists of a certain profile within the framework of organizationally different forms of education. Dual form of education is a method of education, the essence of which is to combine training of persons in educational institutions with training in the workplace at enterprises, institutions and organizations to acquire certain qualifications, usually on the basis of a contract for dual education. education [6]. The system of dual education was established and acquired its primary development within the educational space of Western Europe (Austria, Germany, Switzerland), but the domestic system of vocational training also has a tradition of its development: form of education, and in the format of practical training of higher education full-time students in real jobs "[3].

The legal basis for the introduction of the dual form of education in vocational institutions before higher and higher education in Ukraine is the Law of Ukraine "On Education", 2017, № 2145-VIII (as amended); Law of Ukraine "On Higher Education", 2014, № 1556-VII (as amended); Law of Ukraine "On Professional Higher Education", 2019, 2745-VIII (as amended); Order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated 19.09.2018 № 660-r "On approval of the Concept of training specialists in the dual form of education"; Action plan for the implementation of the Concept of training specialists in the dual form of education, approved by the Order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated 03.04. 2019 №214; Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine dated 13.02. 2019 №175 On approval of the composition of the working group for the implementation of the I and II stages of the Concept of training specialists in the dual form of education; Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine of October 15, 2019 № 1296 "On the introduction of a pilot project in institutions of professional higher and higher education for the training of specialists in the dual form of education."

The analytical report (authors O. Davlikanova, T. Ishchenko, A. Tchaikovsky) presents an analysis of the results of the first year of the pilot project on the introduction of dual education in vocational higher and higher education institutions of Ukraine, describes approaches to organizing cooperation with employers to train applicants education in dual form, studied the views of the parties on the advantages and disadvantages of this form, identified tasks to create favorable conditions for the dissemination of new practices, collected data to refine the regulatory framework [1].

We conducted a study in four regions of Ukraine (Kharkiv, Poltava, Volyn and Luhansk (Ukraine-controlled territory) regions "Expert assessment of students of future professional activity", which was attended by applicants for vocational schools before higher and higher education.

To the question "In your opinion, which of the following factors affects the quality of preparation for future professional activities", respondents gave the following answers: improving the use of premises and equipment - 24.4%; conducting practical classes directly at the factory - 23.1%; the ratio of teachers, masters of industrial training and students - 20.7%; competence of vocational school administration in solving issues of training 17.7%; expansion of international relations of vocational schools - 14.1%.

Fig. 1. The influence of certain factors on the effectiveness of vocational schools

Respondents' answers to the question "Do the professional knowledge, skills and abilities provided to a vocational school student meet the requirements of the scope and level of the labor market?" by regions are given in Table 2. Thus, 85.7% of respondents in Luhansk region believe that the professional knowledge, skills and abilities provided to students of vocational schools, in general, meet the requirements of their volume and level of the labor market; respondents of Kharkiv region have this indicator is 44.4%, and respondents of Poltava region - 37.3%. However, taking into account the answers "almost no", the data are 16.7%, and "probably not" - 11.2% of respondents in Kharkiv region, the answer "almost no" - 5.4% and "probably not" - 9.0 % of respondents in Volyn region, as well as the answer "almost no" - 3.3% and "probably not" - 13.2% of respondents in Poltava region, we can conclude that the

knowledge, skills and abilities that students receive vocational schools, still do not fully meet the requirements of the labor market, which is why it is necessary to improve the quality of their training, and the solution of this problem depends entirely on public administration of this education.

Table 1.

Compliance of professional knowledge, skills and abilities provided to a vocational school student with the requirements of the labor market

Region	Correspondence of professional knowledge, skills and abilities				
	Almost no	Probably not	Correspond in general	Rather yes	Yes
Volyn	5,4 %	9,0 %	26,6 %	20,0 %	39,0 %
Luhansk	0,0 %	0,0 %	85,7 %	12,0 %	2,3 %
Poltava	3,3 %	13,2 %	37,3 %	33,0 %	13,2 %
Kharkiv	16,7 %	11,2 %	44,4 %	22,2 %	5,5 %

Source: [4]

Generalized answers to this question are shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Compliance of professional knowledge, skills and abilities provided to the vocational school student with the requirements of the labor market

Respondents were also asked to assess the significance of the impact of individual training factors on the dual form of education on their further professional

activities. The results of the answers received from the respondents are shown in summary table 2.

Table 2.

Influence of separate factors of training on a dual form of training on the further professional activity of graduates of vocational schools

Factors	Region				General
	Volyn	Luhansk	Poltava	Kharkiv	
1. Combination of knowledge obtained in vocational schools with practice in the workplace	29,0%	21,6%	27,0%	31,6%	27,1%
2. Chance to get the first job immediately after graduation	18,3%	20,3%	23,4%	17,2%	19,7%
3. Have work experience before graduation	13,6%	16,5%	13,2 %	20,5%	15,8%
4. See your own future career	27,0%	21,2%	24,3%	13,2%	21,3%
5. Have a monetary reward in the learning process	14,3%	20,3%	12,8%	17,4%	16,1%

Source: [4]

Generalized answers to this question are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. The influence of certain factors of training in the dual form of education on the further professional activity of graduates of vocational schools

According to the results of the answers, such a factor as the combination of knowledge obtained in a vocational school (VET) with practice in the workplace, has a significant impact on the respondents of the Kharkiv region (31.6%); the chance to get the first job immediately after graduation is more attractive for respondents in Poltava region (23.4%); to have work experience before the end of vocational school is more acceptable for respondents of Kharkiv region (20.5%); for respondents from Volyn region to see their own future career is an attractive indicator (27.0%); respondents from Luhansk region (20.3%) want to have a monetary reward in the process of education more than all respondents.

The dual system of education of the EU countries is characterized by:

- concluding a 3-party agreement on vocational training (enterprise-student-vocational school);
- 70-80% of training takes place in the workplace - 3-4 days a week the student studies at the enterprise and 1-2 days in the school;
- the main costs of vocational training are borne by the company; the company also pays compensation to instructors who are distracted from the main work and engaged in mentoring);
- the student at the enterprise receives a reward (the student's salary averages 80% of the salary of a qualified employee);
- for the education of students there are various state subsidies for enterprises;
- final control of knowledge is carried out by independent commissions of chambers of commerce and industry;
- legislative framework conditions;
- support of the dual system by business, social partners, the state, educational institutions.

After passing the exams, the graduate receives three certificates: vocational school, enterprise and a state-recognized certificate of profession from the Chamber of Commerce. The legislative framework of Germany for the application of the dual

system of vocational education is a number of laws, agreements, regulations, the Constitution: the Law on Vocational Education; Law on labor protection of minors; Regulations on fisheries; Law on Tariff Agreements; Law on Temporary Regulation of the Law of Chambers of Commerce and Industry; Laws on chambers of commerce and industry; Law on Regulation of Enterprises; Regional school laws; Coordination agreement between the regulations of vocational education and the framework curriculum; Constitution - paragraph 12.

In countries such as Germany, Austria, Switzerland, where a dual system of vocational training is used, on average about 40-50% of young people of one year of birth study under this system. For example, one in five German companies is trained in manufacturing, and two-thirds of students are trained in large enterprises in the country. Of those studying at the company, two-thirds remain to work there. Every year, German companies enter into more than half a million vocational education agreements, investing more than 30 billion euros in this field.

In Kazakhstan, for example, more than a hundred organizations of technical and vocational education of branch enterprises introduce elements of dual training in such branches as agriculture, transport, metallurgy, mechanical engineering, oil and chemical production. Enterprises were provided with 170300 jobs for industrial practice; 5 1000 places - orders for training, as well as scholarships are issued to students at the expense of enterprises.

Taking into account the experience of vocational education in Germany, in 2003 at the National Technical University "Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute" (NTU "KhPI", Ukraine) with the support of the Otto von Guericke University of Magdeburg, a German technical faculty was established to train students in mechanical engineering. and electrical engineering profile. Guided by the regulatory framework of Ukraine for dual education, NTU "KhPI" in 2014 began developing and subsequently implementing the Concept of Development of the National Technical University "Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute" for 2016-2025. The purpose of this Concept was to spread creative ties with employers through the creation of training, research and production clusters, the establishment of dual education and public-

private partnerships. One of the strategic directions of development of NTU "KhPI" until 1925 is the spread of the practice of using the dual form of education, public-private partnership of the university with IT companies. The practice of implementing dual-form training shows that the forms of presentation of knowledge, as well as forms of professional skills, are fundamentally different from traditional learning.

The project of implementation of the dual approach to education in the preparation of masters of IT specialties at the Department of "Software Engineering and Information Technology Management" NTU "KhPI" is given in table 4.

Table 4.

Project for the implementation of a dual approach to education in the preparation of masters of IT specialty at the Department of "Software Engineering and Information Technology Management" NTU "KhPI"

Indicators	Factors
Topicality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - growing demand for IT professionals, caused by the increasing importance of the IT sector in the economic development of the state; - the gap between the requirements of employers and the level of training of graduates; - Insufficient level of practical training of specialists by the institution of higher education
Project tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - adaptation of professional knowledge, skills, abilities of graduates to the changing conditions of the labor market; - improving the practical training of senior students; - strengthening the staff of IT companies by young qualified professionals; - creating a competitive environment among students, which ensures the growth of success and motivation
Performance indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the number of students who have successfully completed a master's degree on the basis of a dual approach to education; - the quality of theoretical training of students during the implementation of the dual approach to education (the percentage of those who are engaged in "good" and "excellent"); - the quality of professional activity of students in IT companies, which is assessed on the basis of data on career growth
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - cooperation of the department with IT companies; - the desire of students for successful employment; - interest of IT companies in obtaining new, well-trained staff; - professional staff of the Department of Software Engineering and Information Technology Management;

	- material and technical resources of the department
Risk factors	- efficiency of educational technology; - bureaucracy of higher education; - political instability; - difficult economic situation; - outflow of investments at the state level
Target audience of the project	- students majoring in "software engineering", "computer science" NTU "KhPI"; - IT companies in the cluster, partner companies; - Department of Software Engineering and Information Technologies Management NTU "KhPI"
Innovations in education technology used in the project	- modular programs, - flexible training schedule, - activation of cognition, - control of independent work, - adaptability, active learning, - e-learning, cooperation, - individual approach
Scope	master's programs based on specialties: - "Software Engineering" - "Computer Science", - "Information systems and technologies"

During the training of specialists in the dual form of NTU "KhPI" provides:

- strengthening and improving the practical component of the educational process while maintaining a sufficient level of theoretical training;
- interconnection, interpenetration and interaction of different systems (science and education, science and production or the public sector) to implement important changes aimed at improving the quality of education;
- improving the quality of training in accordance with the real requirements of the labor market and replenish the national economy with qualified professionals;
- strengthening the role of employers and professional associations in the system of training qualified personnel (from the formation of the content of educational programs to the evaluation of learning outcomes);
- modernization of the content of education in order to bring them in line with the modern content of professional activity;

- increasing the level of competitiveness of graduates of educational institutions in the context of globalization and promoting the growth of youth employment;

- reduction of the period of adaptation of graduates to professional activity;

- increasing the motivation of students to study.

According to the State Employment Center, by type of vocational training, employers prefer on-the-job training. "We are talking about the organization of training of trained specialists on the basis of our own enterprise or about raising the professional level of employees or future candidates for jobs on the basis of educational institutions of the state employment service." According to scientists, employers are not ready to take on the function of training employees in accordance with their own requirements, transferring this task to the state or utilities [3].

However, there is experience of active interaction of employers with institutions of higher technical education. Thus, at the National Technical University "Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute" in September 2018 opened a Career Center, whose task is to hold Career Days, work with representatives of graduating departments to select vacancies for students, the formation of an electronic database of employers of higher technical institution education, cooperation with the Kharkiv Regional Employment Center, organization and holding of events to promote the employment of graduates (meetings, presentations, round tables, excursions to enterprises, organizations, companies). Thus, during the planned period of the Career Center (spring semester 2018-2019 academic year) students had the opportunity to visit the brewery "AltBier", to meet with representatives of the brewery "Probka", with representatives of "Procter & Gambel", with representatives of CanInBev, representatives of Landstar Agent Ukraine. Meetings of students with the management of these companies contributed to the establishment of cooperation: internships and employment, interviews, trainings, business games with the winners of online testing; discussion of internship opportunities for students. The Career Development Center aims not only to organize alumni meetings with potential employers, but also to train future professionals for self-employment.

Conclusions and prospects for further research. Based on the study, we came to the following conclusions:

- the introduction of a dual form of education will help to overcome the problem of outdated material and technical base in institutions before higher and higher professional education, will allow employers to get involved in the process of training graduates;

- the use of the experience of the dual form of education of the EU countries in the system before higher and higher professional education will contribute to better professional training of students and their demand in the Ukrainian and world labor markets;

- With the further development of social partnership, consolidation of efforts of central and local executive bodies and local governments, educational institutions, employers, scientists and public associations, it is possible to rise before higher and higher professional education to a qualitatively new level.

We consider the influence of the digitalization process on the professional training of students to be a promising area of further research.

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